

Unusual selectivities of Grignards and organocuprates with formylcoumarins : Stereochemical as well as conformational characteristics of the oxygenheterocycles[†]

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Reactions of Grignards and organocuprates on formylcoumarins; formation of unusual oxygenheterocycles and their conformational and conformational aspects have been described.

The investigation employing bromozinc enolates¹ on 4-formylcoumarin (**2**) and 4-formyl-7-methoxycoumarin (**5**) did produce a large number of new coumarins recording high degree of stereo-, regio-, and chemoselectivity. Excellent diastereoselective synthesis of β -coumarinyl acrylates has also been successfully carried² out by us applying Wittig and Wittig-Horner reagents on formylcoumarins (**2**, **5**). This logically encouraged us to explore further a similar type of methodology employing a fairly large variety of organomagnesium halides on formylcoumarins. It should be emphasised that the earlier studies on the reactions of organomagnesium halides and bromozinc enolates on coumarinyl methyl ketones^{3,4}, not only divulged high degree of selectivities but also produced unusual products. On allowing the Grignards (RMgX; R = Me, Et, Prⁱ, Buⁱ, Ph, *p*-anisyl) to react with 4-formylcoumarin (**2**) and 4-formyl-7-methoxycoumarin (**5**) excellent stereoselectivity as well as unusual courses of reactions could be observed. The outcome of this systematic investigation along with necessary justification constitutes the subject matter of this presentation.

From the reactions with RMgBr (R = Ph, Et, Prⁱ, Buⁱ, *p*-anisyl) the expected chemoselectivity involving a typical 1,2-addition to formyl functionality was recorded producing exclusively the alcohols (**10**, **12**, **13**, **15**, **18**, **20**, **22**, **26**). The structures of all the unknown compounds thus obtained have been unambiguously determined through the extensive application of spectroscopic techniques. Some of the alcohols (**10**, **13**, **18**, **22**) could also be converted to the respective acetates (**11**, **14**, **19**, **23**). Interestingly enough, the reaction between iso-butylmagnesium bromide and **2** failed to produce the expected alcohol through 1,2-addition. Instead it underwent dehydration furnishing **24** in which the olefinic bond could be unequivocally characterised to enjoy Z-

configuration, mainly from its ¹H NMR spectrum wherein the respective olefinic 1'-H appeared as a doublet at δ 3.84 with a ³J value of 7 Hz, typical for *cis*-olefinic proton and 2'-H as a triplet (*J* 7 Hz) at δ 3.88. The relative shielding of signals of 1'-H and 2'-H demands that the side chain at C-4 does not lie in the σ -plane of the coumarin moiety avoiding nonbonded steric interaction between 2'-CHMe₂ and H-3 or H-5 in the respective *S-cis* and *S-trans* conformations of **24** which is only possible with the *cis*-configuration of the olefinic double bonds between 1' and 2' positions. It is quite reasonable to note that in the formation of 1,2-addition products, RMgBr (R = Ph, Et, Prⁱ, Buⁱ, *p*-anisyl) manifests high degree of chemoselectivity in attacking the formylcoumarin (**2** and **5**).

Curiously enough from all the Grignard reactions performed, highly polar reduction products **6** and **7** from **2** and **5** respectively were uniformly obtained in poor yield. The respective acetates **8** and **9** of **6** and **7** were also prepared. The genesis of such reduction products may be accounted for via the initial formation of ketyl radicals, involving a SET mechanism⁵. It is relevant to note at this juncture that such reduction products as alcohols **6** and **7** were also encountered during the reaction of bromozinc enolates¹ with these formylcoumarins (**2**, **5**).

Among the unusual products **16**, **17**, **21** and **25**, the former two were obtained following a different course of reactions when formylcoumarins **2** and **5** were allowed to react with MeMgI in dry THF under nitrogen atmosphere. Spectral characteristics of **16** and **17** indicate the presence of a new δ -lactone moiety without having an α,β -unsaturation. Most plausibly the reaction is proceeding through an 1,4-addition to coumarin α,β -unsaturated δ -lactone moiety as an initial step followed by an 1,2-addition to aldehyde function. Thus the reaction of CH₃MgI on

[†]Dedicated to Professor S. M. Mukherji.

formylcoumarin appears to be considerably less chemoselective as it undergoes both 1,2- as well as 1,4-additions.

The relative configuration of **16** and **17** may logically be represented as **28** and **29** respectively. In the ^1H NMR spectra of **16** and **17** the appearance of hydroxy proton signal as a sharp singlet at δ 5.4 demands that it is most likely intramolecularly hydrogen bonded, necessitating further that the δ -lactone moiety is in boat conformation. In such a conformation intramolecular hydrogen bonding is only possible if the hydroxy group at C-1' attaches itself to the carbon chain located at the flagpole disposition as shown in **28** and **29**. It should be emphasised that this sort of intramolecular hydrogen bonding turns out to be not an uncommon feature in 4-hydroxytetrahydropyran system⁶ wherein the ring has to assume a boat conformation in order to accommodate such hydrogen bonding. The relative configuration of C-4 and C-1' could be settled from their ^1H NMR spectra wherein H-3 and H'-3 appear as a pair of doublets at δ 2.50 and δ 3.01 with J 16 Hz whereas H-1' appears as a distinctly fine quartet (J 7 Hz) at δ 5.1 demanding that there is no spin information exchange between the protons located at C-1' and C-3. Obviously this will turn out to be a possibility if H-1' and H-3 or H'-3 fail to maintain a W-type disposition which always involves a long range coupling (4J) of appreciable magnitude (~ 4 Hz)^{1,7}. Hence it is reasonable to conclude that the configuration of C-4 and C-1' will be $4R^*$, $1'S^*$ as shown. However, the compounds are formed in (\pm)-form. The conclusion drawn so far gets full support from all the spectral evidence including ^{13}C NMR study which is also perfectly compatible with the literature⁸.

Turning our attention to the coumaranones (**21**, **25**) as abnormal products, it is gratifying to note that they could be characterised by reacting 4-formylcoumarin (**2**) with isopropylmagnesium bromide and 4-formyl-7-methoxycoumarin (**5**) with iso-butylmagnesium bromide. Interestingly enough these compounds also display the presence of an α,β -unsaturated γ -lactone moiety instead of an α,β -unsaturated δ -lactone and could be ultimately identified as 3-alkylidene-2-coumaranone derivatives (**21**, **25**). To our pleasant surprise the corresponding reduction products as alcohols **6** and **7** have also been isolated along with the coumaranones **21** and **25** respectively. The configuration of the double bond in α,β -unsaturated ester function in **21** and **25** has been established to be *E*, from a detailed mechanistic consideration of its genesis as delineated in the sequel. Possibly at the initial stage oxygen reacts³ with the respective Grignards, RMgX ($\text{R} = \text{Pr}^i, \text{Bu}^i$) resulting in the formation of the corresponding hydroperoxide ROOMgX . Subsequent reduction of the generated hydroperoxide by a fresh molecule of

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|---|--|
| 1 R, R ¹ , R ² = H | 6 R, R ¹ = H; R ² = OH |
| 2 R = H; R ¹ , R ² = O | 7 R = OMe; R ¹ = H; R ² = OH |
| 3 R = OH; R ¹ , R ² = H | 8 R, R ¹ = H; R ² = OAc |
| 4 R = OMe; R ¹ , R ² = H | 9 R = OMe; R ¹ = H; R ² = OAc |
| 5 R = OMe; R ¹ , R ² = O | |

- | | | |
|--------------------|--|----------------------|
| 10 R = H; | R ¹ = Ph; | R ² = OH |
| 11 R = H; | R ¹ = Ph; | R ² = OAc |
| 12 R = OMe; | R ¹ = Ph; | R ² = OH |
| 13 R = H; | R ¹ = <i>p</i> -anisyl; | R ² = OH |
| 14 R = H; | R ¹ = <i>p</i> -anisyl; | R ² = OAc |
| 15 R = OMe; | R ¹ = <i>p</i> -anisyl; | R ² = OH |
| 18 R = H; | R ¹ = C ₂ H ₅ ; | R ² = OH |
| 19 R = H; | R ¹ = C ₂ H ₅ ; | R ² = OAc |
| 20 R = OMe; | R ¹ = C ₂ H ₅ ; | R ² = OH |
| 22 R = OMe; | R ¹ = Pr ⁱ ; | R ² = OH |
| 23 R = OMe; | R ¹ = Pr ⁱ ; | R ² = OAc |

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|--------------------|--|
| 24 R = H; | R ¹ , R ² = CHCHMe_2 |
| 26 R = OMe; | R ¹ = Bu ⁱ ; R ² = OH |

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|---|---|
| 16 R = H; R ¹ = CH ₃ | 21 R = H; R ¹ = Pr ⁱ |
| 17 R = OMe; R ¹ = CH ₃ | 25 R = OMe; R ¹ = Bu ⁱ |
| 27 R = OMe; R ¹ = C ₂ H ₅ | |

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| 28 R = H; R ¹ = Me |
| 29 R = OMe; R ¹ = Me |
| 30 R = OMe; R ¹ = Et |

Grignard affords ultimately an alkoxy magnesium halide, ROMgX^3 which is actually responsible for the formation of the abnormal products **21** and **25** as depicted in Scheme 1.

Thus 1,2-addition of ROMgX to δ -lactone carbonyl of **2** and **5** affords intermediate **I** which on rotation about the σ -bond between C-4 and C-4a passes on to **II**. A 5-exo-trig cyclisation of **II** leads to intermediate **III** which most reasonably during work up passes on to **IV**. Most plausibly subsequent aerial oxidation of **IV** leads to the unusual prod-

Scheme 1. Genesis of **21** and **25** ($\text{R} = \text{Pr}^i$, $\text{R}^1 = \text{H}$; $\text{R} = \text{Bu}^i$, $\text{R}^1 = \text{OMe}$).

ucts **21** and **25**. It must be mentioned at this stage that a similar sort of involvement of alkoxy magnesium halide was successfully established by us leading to abnormal product formation during the reaction of alkylmagnesium halides on 7-methoxy-8-coumarinyl methyl ketone³. It should be stressed that such unusual product formation due to the involvement of oxygen could only be observed with alkyl Grignards and not with aryl Grignards not only with formylcoumarins in the present study but also with coumarinyl methylketones reported earlier³.

Replacing the harder base Grignard, formylcoumarin, **5** was subsequently allowed to react with a much softer base organocuprates⁹ which were prepared by adding dry cuprous cyanide in 0.07 molar percent of Grignards, keeping the reaction under nitrogen cover. Column chromatography of the crude product could afford a pure sample of **27** which is formed through 1,4-addition to α,β -unsaturated coumarin δ -lactone function followed by an 1,2-addition to aldehyde functionality. It is quite unusual to note that the corresponding reduction product as alcohol **7** has also been identified from this course of reactions of organocuprates. Regarding the relative configuration and preferred conformation of **27** it may be stated that it should be represented as **30** since it displays characteristic spectral properties which are very similar to that of **16** and **17** discussed earlier.

The study carried out so far records the unusual behaviour of Grignards and organocuprates in the formation of (i) coumaranones (**21**, **25**) involving ROOMgX, (ii) coumarinyl carbinols (**6**, **7**) as reduction products following SET mechanism, (iii) simultaneous 1,2- as well as 1,4-addition products (**16**, **17**, **27**) with excellent diastereoselectivity. To our knowledge such observations are almost absent in the literature. In order to draw a definite conclusion it is highly pertinent to compare the results of our previous studies¹⁻⁴ with those of the present investigation in a nutshell.

Though with coumarinyl methyl ketones Grignard reactions turn out to be much less chemoselective, present investigation clearly demonstrates that such reactions on formylcoumarins record much higher degree of chemoselectivity. Only with 7-methoxy-8-coumarinyl ketone oxygen uniformly intervened in the reaction of alkyl Grignards and not aryl Grignards. However with formylcoumarins involvement of oxygen could be definitely established only with *i*-PrMgBr and *i*-BuMgBr. Moreover it has also been observed that formylcoumarins are more inclined to undergo reduction whereas coumarinyl methyl ketone is totally reluctant to undergo any reduction with Grignards. Quite interestingly reactions of much softer reagent organocuprates record poor chemoselectivity. In order to understand more comprehensively the nature of selectivities which could be offered by Grignards and organocuprates on coumarin derivatives bearing a further electrophilic centre, the present study unequivocally corroborates that a detailed and exhaustive study on the subject turns out to be absolutely essential selecting judiciously varieties of coumarinyl ketone and formylcoumarin as effective substrate.

Experimental

General remarks :

All melting points and boiling points are uncorrected. UV spectra were measured in aldehyde free 95% ethanol in Hitachi U-2000 spectrophotometer. IR spectra were recorded in KBr with a Hitachi 270-30 Data processor. The ¹H NMR spectra were determined in deuteriochloroform on JEOL FX100 FT spectrometer and Hitach 600 FT NMR spectrometer using TMS as an internal standard. Mass spectra were recorded on Finnigan Mat 1020C Mass spectrophotometer at 70 eV and Shimadzu Model GEMS QP 1000A Mass spectrometer. ¹³C NMR spectra were run on JEOL FX100 spectrometer. All yields are calculated on the basis of the recovery (~25%) of starting material. In all the reactions 1 mole of substrate was allowed to react with 4 moles of Grignard reagent. Preparation of 4-formylcoumarin (**2**) from 4-methylcoumarin (**1**) and 7-

methoxy-4-formylcoumarin (**5**) from 7-methoxy-4-methylcoumarin (**4**) by selenium dioxide oxidation, preparation of **4** through methylation of 4-methyl-7-hydroxycoumarin (**3**) and preparations of **1** and **3** have been described earlier¹.

Preparation of Grignards and its reaction with 2 and 5 employing various alkyl and arylmagnesium halides : General procedure : Grignard reagent was prepared by refluxing the respective alkyl or aryl halides with Mg turnings (22.28 mmol : 22.28 mmol) in dry THF (30 ml) for 5 h. To it 4-formylcoumarin (**2**, 1 g; 5.75 mmol) or 4-formyl-7-methoxycoumarin (**5**, 1 g; 5 mmol) in dry THF was added dropwise with stirring under nitrogen atmosphere and was left overnight. It was decomposed carefully using 100 ml of ice cold dilute aqueous hydrochloric acid solution and was extracted with chloroform (5 × 25 ml). The combined chloroform extract was washed with saturated brine (3 × 20 ml) and was dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. Evaporation of solvent afforded solid/semisolid mass which was subjected to usual TLC and column chromatography over silica gel to get all the pure products (**6**, **7**, **10**, **12**, **13**, **15**, **16**, **17**, **18**, **20**, **21**, **22**, **24**, **25**, **26**) which were unambiguously characterised⁺ along with the recovered starting material **2** and **5**.

Preparation of acetates : The respective alcohol **6**, **7**, **10**, **13**, **18** and **22** (200 mg) was treated with distilled acetic anhydride (0.5 ml) and fused sodium acetate (30 mg). It was warmed in a water-bath and subsequently left overnight under dry condition. It was finally decomposed with dilute hydrochloric acid followed by neutralisation with sodium bicarbonate. It was extracted with chloroform (3 × 10 ml) and the combined chloroform extract was washed with saturated brine (3 × 15 ml). Evaporation of the solvent furnished a solid which was crystallised from chloroform and petrol (60–80°) mixture to get the pure acetates (**8**, **9**, **11**, **14**, **19**, **23**).

Grignard reaction of 4-formyl-7-methoxycoumarin (5) with an organocuprate, EtCu (CN) MgBr : EtMgBr was prepared by adding ethyl bromide (2.18 g; 20 mmol) to a stirred suspension of magnesium turnings (0.480 g, 20 mmol) with a pinch of iodine in dry THF (30 ml) under nitrogen atmosphere. When all the magnesium got consumed, solid CuCN (0.179 g; 20 mmol) was added and it was stirred further for 5 mins to get EtCu (CN) MgBr in THF solution. To it 4-formyl-7-methoxycoumarin (**5**, 1 g; 5

mmol) in 50 ml of dry THF was added dropwise under nitrogen atmosphere. When the addition has been over it was stirred for 4 h and left overnight. After decomposing it with ice cold saturated NH₄Cl solution (100 ml) it was extracted with chloroform (3 × 30 ml) and the combined extract was washed with cold saturated aqueous brine solution (3 × 30 ml) and finally dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. Removal of solvent afforded a semisolid mass which was chromatographed over silica gel to get **27** in pure form.

10 yield 35.7%, m.p. 114°, C₁₆H₁₂O₃; IR : 3400, 1722, 1600 cm⁻¹; UV : 210.5 (log ε 4.05), 313.0 (2.98); ¹H NMR : 3.56 (1H, broad s, OH), 5.94 (1H, s, CHOH), 6.73 (1H, s, 3-H), 7.12 to 7.62 (9H, complex, Ar-H); MS : 252 (53.8, •M⁺), 235 (4.20, •M⁺-•OH), 234 (15.5, •M⁺-H₂O), 224 (4.5, •M⁺-CO), 223 (•M⁺-CO-•H), 206 (12.1), 205 (3.2), 195 (3.4), 181 (3.6), 179 (4.8), 178 (13.3), 177 (4.7), 176 (5.0, •M⁺-•C₆H₅+•H), 167 (2.4), 158 (5.9), 151 (3.1), 148 (2.6), 147 (26.3, •M⁺-•C₆H₅-CO), 145 (3.5, •M⁺-•C₆H₅-CO-2•H), 131 (2.4), 119 (10.8), 117 (8.86, m/z 145-CO), 115 (8.6), 107 (10.5, Ph-CH=O+H), 106 (6.2, PhCH•O⁺), 105 (100-PhC≡O⁺).

11 yield 83.3%, m.p. 118°, C₁₈H₁₄O₄; IR : 1728, 1605 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR : 2.18 (3H, s, COCH₃), 6.68 (1H, s, 3-H), 7.13 to 7.50 (10H, complex, 9Ar-H and CH-OAc)

12 yield 35.2%, m.p. 164°, C₁₇H₁₄O₄; IR : 3395, 1720, 1610 cm⁻¹; UV : 210 (log ε 3.98), 323 (3.21); ¹H NMR : 2.34 (1H, d, J 4 Hz, OH), 3.84 (3H, s, OCH₃), 6.05 (1H, d, J 4 Hz, CHOH), 6.69 (1H, s, 3-H), 6.72 (1H, d, J 2 Hz, 8-H), 6.80 (1H, dd, J 2, 7 Hz, 6-H), 7.26 (1H, d, J 7 Hz, 5-H), 7.40 to 7.42 (5H, complex, Ar-H); MS : 282 (100, •M⁺), 281 (2.2, •M⁺-•H), 267 (1.2, •M⁺-•Me), 264 (3.6, •M⁺-H₂O), 237 (23.2, •M⁺-•OH-CO), 194 (4.6), 191 (1.4), 163 (16.8), 151 (6.3), 149 (56.1), 148 (11.6), 131 (1.6), 128 (1.3), 127 (1.6), 126 (1.6), 124 (4.6), 122 (8.5), 121 (18.3), 120 (3.3), 119 (7.6), 118 (2.5), 115 (8.9).

13 yield 34.7%, m.p. 75°, C₁₇H₁₄O₄; IR : 3432, 1718, 1606 cm⁻¹; UV : 209 (log ε 3.37), 323 (3.11); ¹H NMR : 3.72 (3H, s, OCH₃), 5.98 (1H, s, CHOH), 6.75 (1H, s, 3-H), 6.82 to 7.40 (8H, complex, Ar-H).

14 yield 85.7%, m.p. 105°, C₁₉H₁₆O₅; IR : 1724, 1672, 1604 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR : 2.17 (3H, s, COCH₃), 3.78 (3H, s, OCH₃), 6.69 to 7.45 (10H, complex, Ar-H and 3-H and CHOAc).

15 yield 34.3%, m.p. 130°, C₁₈H₁₆O₅; IR : 3388, 1702, 1608 cm⁻¹; UV : 208.5 (log ε 3.52), 323 (3.26); ¹H NMR : 3.82 (6H, s, 7-OMe, anisyl OMe), 5.95 (1H, d, J 4 Hz, CHOH), 6.71 (1H, s, 3-H), 6.80 to 7.41 (7-H, complex, Ar-H). **16** yield 37.9%, m.p. 159°, C₁₂H₁₄O₃; IR : 3392,

⁺Physical and microanalytical data of all the new compounds have been found to be fully consistent with the structures proposed. Spectral characteristics of the new compounds have been enumerated at the end of the experimental.

1736, 1612 cm^{-1} ; UV : 215.5 (log ϵ 3.71), 274.5 (3.56); ^1H NMR : 1.10 (3H, d, J 7 Hz, 1'- CH_3), 1.52 (3H, s, 4- CH_3), 2.50 (1H, d, J 16 Hz, 3-H), 3.11 (1H, d, J 16 Hz, 3-H'), 5.10 (1H, q, J 7 Hz, 1'-H), 5.44 (1H, s, OH), 6.72 to 7.27 (4H, complex, Ar-H).

17 yield 37.8%, m.p. 150°, $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_4$; IR : 3296, 1738, 1616 cm^{-1} ; UV : 216.5 (log ϵ 3.78), 279.0 (3.54); ^1H NMR : 1.07 (3H, d, J 7 Hz, 1'- CH_3), 1.48 (3H, s, 4- CH_3), 2.28 (1H, d, J 16 Hz, 3-H), 3.08 (1H, d, J 16 Hz, 3-H'), 3.76 (3H, s, OCH_3), 5.03 (1H, q, J 7 Hz, 1'-H), 5.37 (1H, s, OH), 6.32 (1H, d, J 2 Hz, 8-H), 6.46 (1H, dd, J 2, 7 Hz, 6-H), 6.92 (1H, d, J 7 Hz, 5-H); MS : 236 (8.6, $\bullet\text{M}^+$), 221 (2.96, $\bullet\text{M}^+ \cdot \text{CH}_3$), 192 (35.2, $\bullet\text{M}^+ \cdot \text{CH}_3 \cdot \text{CO} \cdot \text{H}$), 191 (66.3, $\bullet\text{M}^+ \cdot \text{CHOHMe}$), 177 (26.6, m/z 192- $\bullet\text{Me}$), 164 (100, m/z 192-CO), 149 (47.2, m/z 164- $\bullet\text{Me}$), 135 (11.6), 133 (5.25), 121 (29.6), 115 (6.4), 105 (11.6), 103 (16.3), 91 (33.0), 78 (15.0), 77 (38.6), 69 (18.9), 65 (15.0), 60 (4.3), 55 (15.9); ^{13}C NMR : 177.4 (s, C-2), 159.9 (s, C-9), 154.5 (s, C-7), 128.8 (d, C-5), 121.9 (s, C-10), 105.1 (d, C-6), 102.7 (d, C-8), 86.4 (d, C-1'), 55.3 (q, 7-OMe), 46.3 (s, C-4), 40.2 (t, C-3), 26.2 (q, 4-Me), 17.9 (q, 1'-Me).

18 yield 41.07%, m.p. 119°, $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_3$; IR : 3428, 1700, 1606 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR : 1.06 (3H, t, J 7.2 Hz, CH_2CH_3), 1.81 (2H, distorted quin, J 7.2 Hz, CH_2CH_3), 3.01 (1H, broad s, OH), 5.01 (1H, broad t, J 7.2 Hz, CHOH), 6.61 (1H, s, 3-H), 7.10 to 7.75 (4H, complex, Ar-H).

19 yield 78.2%, m.p. 84°, $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_4$; IR : 1724, 1620, 1606 cm^{-1} ; UV : 210.5 (log ϵ 3.21), 326.0 (2.98); ^1H NMR : 1.02 (3H, t, J 6.6 Hz, CH_2CH_3), 1.73 (2H, distorted quin, J 6.6 Hz, CH_2CH_3), 2.18 (3H, s, COCH_3), 6.02 (1H, distorted t, J 6.6 Hz, CHOAc), 6.45 (1H, s, 3-H), 7.20 to 7.80 (4H, complex, Ar-H).

20 yield 29.6%, b.p. 92–95°/0.3–0.5 mm, $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_4$; IR : 3400, 1725, 1601 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR : 1.04 (3H, t, J 7.2 Hz, CH_2CH_3), 1.80 (2H, distorted quin, J 7.2 Hz, CH_2CH_3), 2.68 (1H, board, OH), 3.80 (3H, s, OCH_3), 4.93 (1H, broad t, J 7.2 Hz, CHOH), 6.42 (1H, s, 3-H), 6.75 (1H, d, J 3 Hz, 8-H), 6.81 (1H, dd, J 3, 8 Hz, 6-H), 7.57 (1H, d, J 8 Hz, 5-H); MS : 234 (100, $\bullet\text{M}^+$), 219 (3.8, $\bullet\text{M}^+ \cdot \text{Me}$), 206 (33.4, $\bullet\text{M}^+ \cdot \text{CO}$), 204 (1.9, $\bullet\text{M}^+ \cdot \text{CH}_2\text{O}$), 201 (3.3, $\bullet\text{M}^+ \cdot \text{Me} \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$), 199 (10.4), 190 (9.9), 189 (10.4), 178 (32.7), 177 (53.7), 163 (6.3), 149 (68.8), 121 (42.0), 91 (12.5).

21 yield 30.7%, m.p. 100°, $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_4$; IR : 1736, 1724, 1602 cm^{-1} ; UV : 209.0 (log ϵ 4.93), 291.0 (4.16); ^1H NMR : 1.40 (6H, d, J 7 Hz, CO_2CHMe_2), 5.33 (1H, septate, J 7 Hz, COOCHMe_2), 6.91 (1H, s, 1'-H), 7.16 to 7.68 (3H, complex, 5-H, 6-H and 7-H), 8.27 (1H, dd, J 2, 7 Hz, 4-H); MS : 232 (73.4, $\bullet\text{M}^+$), 190 (35.6, $\bullet\text{M}^+ \cdot \text{CH}_3 \cdot \text{CH}=\text{CH}_2$), 174 (12.0, $\bullet\text{M}^+ \cdot \text{OPr}^i + \text{H}$), 173 (27.0, $\bullet\text{M}^+ \cdot \text{OPr}^i$), 162

(42.5, $\bullet\text{M}^+ \cdot \text{CH}_3 \cdot \text{CH}=\text{CH}_2 \cdot \text{CO}$), 145 (100, $\bullet\text{M}^+ \cdot \text{OPr}^i \cdot \text{CO}$), 118 (22.7), 100 (25.8), 90 (10.3).

22 yield 42.6%, m.p. 130°, $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_4$; IR : 3072, 1716, 1606 cm^{-1} ; UV : 209.0 (log ϵ 3.84), 322.0 (3.07); ^1H NMR : 0.94 (3H, d, J 7 Hz, 2'- CH_3), 1.06 (3H, d, J 7 Hz, 2'- CH_3), 1.67 (1H, broad s, OH), 2.8 (1H, multiplet, CHMe_2), 3.86 (3H, s, OCH_3), 4.74 (1H, complex, CHOH), 6.39 (1H, s, 3-H), 6.79 to 7.66 (3H, complex, Ar-H).

23 yield 81.0%, m.p. 99°, $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_5$; IR : 1726, 1606 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR : 0.93 and 1.05 (each 3H, d, J 7 Hz, CHMe_2), 1.76 (1H, multiplet, CHMe_2), 2.16 (3H, s, COCH_3), 3.87 (3H, s, OCH_3), 5.28 (1H, d, J 7 Hz, CHOAc), 6.23 (1H, s, 3-H), 6.37 (1H, d, J 7 Hz, 8-H), 7.25 to 7.67 (2H, complex, 5-H, 6-H).

24 yield 27.5%, b.p. 80–83°/0.3–0.5 mm, $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_2$; IR : 1730, 1608 cm^{-1} ; UV : 211.0 (log ϵ 4.42), 310.0 (3.87); ^1H NMR : 0.80 (3H, d, J 7 Hz, 3'- CH_3), 0.96 (3H, d, J 7 Hz, 3'- CH_3), 1.76 (1H, complex, 3'-H), 3.88 (1H, t, J 7 Hz, 2'-H), 3.84 (1H, d, J 7 Hz, 1'-H), 6.20 (1H, s, 3-H), 6.70 (1H, dd, J 2, 7 Hz, 8-H), 7.27 (2H, dt, J 7, 2 Hz, 6-H and 7-H), 7.48 (1H, dd, J 2, 7 Hz, 5-H).

25 yield 36.5% m.p. 56°, $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_5$; IR : 1736, 1720, 1636, 1614 cm^{-1} ; UV : 226.0 (log ϵ 4.05), 209.0 (4.67), 282.0 (4.08), 344.0 (4.00); ^1H NMR : 1.03 (6H, d, J 7 Hz, $\text{CO}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CHMe}_2$), 2.00 (1H, nonate, J 7 Hz, $\text{CO}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CHMe}_2$), 3.84 (3H, s, OCH_3), 4.21 (2H, d, J 7 Hz, $\text{CO}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CHMe}_2$), 6.85 (1H, d, J 2 Hz, 7-H), 6.90 (1H, dd, J 2, 7 Hz, 5-H), 7.27 (1H, s, 1'-H), 8.20 (1H, d, J 7 Hz, 4-H); MS : 276 (54.1, $\bullet\text{M}^+$), 262 (14.2), 248 (6.8, $\bullet\text{M}^+ \cdot \text{CO}$), 234 (4.1, $\bullet\text{M}^+ \cdot \text{MeCH}=\text{CH}_2$), 220 (54.9, $\bullet\text{M}^+ \cdot \text{CH}_2=\text{CMe}_2$), 204 (16.3, $\bullet\text{M}^+ \cdot \text{OBu}^i + \text{H}$), 203 (21.0, $\bullet\text{M}^+ \cdot \text{OBu}^i$), 192 (100, $\bullet\text{M}^+ \cdot \text{CO} \cdot \text{CH}_2=\text{CMe}_2$), 177 (35.6), 176 (23.6, m/z 204-CO), 175 (36.9, m/z 192- $\bullet\text{OH}$), 148 (61.4, m/z 192- CO_2), 131 (30.5), 119 (31.8), 88 (9.9), 75 (17.2), 76 (21.8), 69 (12.9), 65 (15.0), 57 (23.6).

26 yield 38.5%, m.p. 102°, $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_4$; IR : 3380, 1724, 1618 cm^{-1} ; UV : 214.0 (log ϵ 3.81), 321.5 (3.94); ^1H NMR : 0.98 (3H, d, J 6 Hz, 3'- CH_3), 1.08 (3H, d, J 6 Hz, 3'- CH_3), 1.64 (2H, complex, CH_2CHMe_2), 2.08 (1H, multiplet, CH_2CHMe_2), 3.86 (3H, s, OCH_3), 5.08 (1H, dd, J 4, 10 Hz, CHOH), 6.46 (1H, s, 3-H), 6.88 (1H, d, J 2 Hz, 8-H), 6.86 (1H, dd, J 2, 7 Hz, 6-H), 7.53 (1H, d, J 7 Hz, 5-H).

27 yield 38.8%, b.p. 98–103°/0.3–0.5 mm, $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}_4$; IR : 3376, 1746, 1618 cm^{-1} ; UV : 208.5 (log ϵ 3.23), 279.0 (3.55); ^1H NMR : 0.59 (3H, t, J 7 Hz, 2'- CH_3), 0.93 (3H, t, J 7 Hz, 1'- CH_3), 1.66 (2H, q, J 7 Hz, 1''- H_2), 2.26 (2H, distorted quintet, J 7 Hz, 2'- H_2), 2.60 (1H, d, J 16 Hz, 3-H), 2.92 (1H, d, J 16 Hz, 3-H'), 3.76 (3H, s, OMe), 4.80

(1H, dd, J 4, 10 Hz, 1'-H), 6.16 to 6.26 (2H, complex, Ar-H), 6.80 (1H, d, J 7 Hz, 5-H).

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References

1. L. N. Dutta, M. Bhattacharyya and A. K. Sarkar, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1995, **73**, 1556.
2. L. N. Dutta and P. K. De, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1998, **75**, 684.
3. L. N. Dutta, N. C. Sinha and A. K. Sarkar, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1991, **30**, 1112.
4. L. N. Dutta, N. C. Sinha and A. K. Sarkar, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1988, **27**, 801.
5. E. C. Ashby and T. L. Wisemen, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1978, **100**, 3101.
6. E. L. Eliel and S. H. Wilen, "Stereochemistry of Organic Compounds", Wiley, New York, 1994, p. 740.
7. R. M. Silverstein and F. X. Webster, "Spectrometric Identification of Organic Compounds", 6th. ed., John Wiley and Sons, New York, 1998, p. 187.
8. W. J. Cussans and T.W. Huckerby, *Tetrahedron*, 1975, **31**, 2719.
9. B. H. Lipshutz and S. Sengupta, "Organocopper Reagents in Organic Reactions", ed. L. A. Paquette, John Wiley and Sons Inc, 1992, Vol. 41, p. 135.